

Leading the charge in partner collaboration: Sofics' IP solutions are strengthening Europe's position in chip design

Best practice category

New impetus for chip design, Partner collaboration

Stakeholder group

SMEs and startups

Value chain position

R&D, IP

General Information

Sofics, headquartered in Gistel, Belgium, is a globally recognised provider of IP for semiconductor electrostatic discharge (ESD) solutions.

Since its founding in 2000, Sofics has been at the forefront of creating innovative ESD protection technologies that enhance performance and robustness while reducing design time and cost of SoC design. The Belgian firm boasts a strong commitment to R&D and has formed partnerships with major foundries to streamline its work.

Sofics is recognised in this list for setting Best Practices in New impetus for chip design and Partner collaboration. The company's pioneering work in ESD solutions and semiconductor IP significantly contributes to the longevity and reliability of advanced electronic devices and strengthens Europe's position in the chip design value chain.

Activities and best practices

Sofics has set itself apart from other companies in the ecosystem by creating strong relationships with key foundries like [TSMC](#), [UMC](#), [Intel](#) and [GlobalFoundries](#), among others. By utilising the fabs' manufacturing capabilities, Sofics guarantees its global network of 100+ companies privileged access to the most advanced solutions in on-chip ESD protection.

One of Sofics' flagship offerings lies in their [TakeCharge® ESD](#) portfolio, which provides tailored ESD protection solutions for a wide range of semiconductor technologies (incl. CMOS, SOI, FinFET and FD-SOI). These solutions are designed to meet the stringent requirements of modern electronic devices, ensuring that they can withstand high-voltage/current discharges without compromising their functionality or reliability. Sofics' innovative approach also extends to the development of [latch-up immune solutions](#), which are particularly important in harsh environments and mission-critical applications. The ESD and latch-up services are used by companies in a wide range of sectors, including automotive, consumer electronics, IoT, medical devices, and space, as well as AI. Overall, Sofics' IP portfolio boasts over 70 patents, which together contribute to a reduction in IC costs, as well as an increase in IC robustness and performance for its clients.

Moreover, the company excels in the Partner collaboration category as one of the founding members of [Flanders Semiconductors](#), as well as its strong partnership with research institutes like [imec](#) and the 10 main semiconductor foundries globally.

Flanders Semiconductors is a network of Flemish semiconductor companies that aims to “boost the visibility and prominence of companies in the Flanders region and beyond.” It was set up as a non-profit organisation to increase the talent pool, share industry roadmaps, maintain a yearly business events calendar, and represent members' interests at European and international levels.

Finally, Sofics is active in R&D – its engineers are heavily involved in validating IP on the newest process nodes and looking for new solutions like low-leakage overvoltage tolerant I/O circuits and high bandwidth interfaces. Maintaining a strong activity in R&D ensures that Sofics stays ahead of the newest developments in technology.

Challenges addressed with this practice

Sofics' commitment to innovation and nurturing its partner collaborations addresses several critical challenges in the electronics industry. Their advanced ESD solutions help mitigate the risks of device failure that occur due to electrostatic discharge, a common and potentially costly issue in semiconductor manufacturing and end-use environments. Additionally, Sofics cultivates its partnerships with leading fabs all around the world. This ensures that its IP is compatible with the latest processing technologies, thus enabling its clients to develop ever smaller, more powerful, and more reliable electronic devices. Through these commitments, Sofics plays a vital role in advancing the capabilities of the global semiconductor ecosystem, and remains an important example of a European semiconductor success story.